

1 Novel soil biological activity sensors can track the recovery of
2 microbial decomposition following the removal of
3 environmental stress

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11 **Keywords**

12 Decomposition, sensors, dynamic monitoring, microbial activity, printed electronics, low-cost
13 sensing

14 **Highlights**

- 15 • Low cost soil decomposition sensor captures dynamics of decomposition
16 • High temporal resolution sensing of soil microbial activity
17 • Recovery of soil microbial activity following stress tracked through time
18 • Evidence of sustained microbial activity in flooded soils with wheat plants

19

20 Graphical Abstract

21

22 Abstract

23 There is a need to measure soil decomposition rates at high spatial and temporal resolution. To
 24 do this, continuous, *in-situ*, non-destructive methods of assessing microbial activity are essential.
 25 Here we demonstrate a method to track decomposition of soil organic matter in real time, using
 26 sensors that are based on a biodegradable composite material which changes its resistance in
 27 response to microbial activity in the soil. These sensors are fabricated using printing techniques
 28 and provide a straightforward resistive readout, enabling their interrogation with simple low-cost
 29 electronic systems, thereby providing a path to wide-scale deployment to provide spatial and
 30 temporal characterization of soil decomposition rates. Using these sensors, microbially-derived
 31 decomposition was monitored on a species rich grassland soil and a monoculture wheat soil,
 32 subjected to either a drought or flooding treatment with a subsequent recovery period. The
 33 sensors were able to track soil decomposition through time at high temporal and spatial
 34 resolution with decomposition activity subdued by the drought and demonstrate recovery
 35 following its cessation. Flooding produced a similar response in the species rich grassland, albeit
 36 the recovery was slower. However, in wheat soil, flooding did not reduce decomposition of the

37 sensor which we attribute to wheat maintaining an oxygenated rhizosphere. The developed
38 sensors can shed light on the dynamic nature of soil microbial processes that would otherwise
39 have gone unobserved.

40 **Keywords**

41 Soil decomposition, sensor, microbial activity, respiration

42 **1 Introduction**

43 The role that healthy soils play in supporting ecosystem function and food production has
44 received increasing attention in recent years. The need to understand changes in soil health has
45 resulted in several indicators being developed for soil health assessment , which commonly
46 include parameters relating to soil carbon (Lehmann et al., 2020). Carbon-based molecules form
47 the basis of soil organic matter, which is a key variable in governing nutrient release, water
48 holding capacity and soil fertility (Hoffland et al., 2020). Understanding the factors that affect
49 buildup and decomposition of organic matter is critical, but predicting these processes is difficult
50 due to the complex interplay between abiotic conditions, plant community structure and function,
51 and microbial activity. Typically, soil chemical, physical and biological parameters are
52 determined at one point in time, either in the field or in the laboratory. Many indicators vary
53 spatially and temporally, yet, except for a few physical and chemical parameters e.g. soil
54 moisture content and electrical conductivity, temporal resolution is limited to the time-point
55 when the samples were taken. Measurements of enzymatic activity, soil nutrient concentrations
56 and soil texture usually need to be taken through destructive soil collection, which causes
57 problems for repeated sampling. Therefore, the options for monitoring the temporal changes in
58 soil biological activity are extremely limited.

59 Field methods for determining soil biological activity have been based on the central role of
60 decomposition in biologically mediated soil processes. The need for a standardised approach
61 that can provide robust results that respond to changes in soil conditions, which have either been
62 imposed by soil management practices or are in response to wider environmental changes, is
63 well recognised (Middleton et al., 2021; Keuskamp et al., 2013; Hayes et al., 2024).
64 Nevertheless, to date it has been difficult to produce dynamic data since the available methods
65 depend upon mass loss and this requires time. Therefore, understanding how decomposition rates

66 fluctuate in response to changes in the soil environment which take place over time periods of
67 hours or days has proved elusive, with scientists relying on the use of CO₂ gas emissions from
68 soil surfaces to generate proxy data with increased temporal resolution.

69 CO₂ emitted at the soil surface results from both the decomposition process and the respiration
70 associated with plant roots and, therefore, represents the net response of soil organisms and
71 plants to changing environmental conditions (Ryan and Law, 2005) and is not solely a measure
72 of soil organism activity. For studies requiring high spatial and temporal resolution, closed
73 chamber methods have become the go to methodology as a surrogate for soil biological activity.
74 High temporal resolution can be achieved through a long-term sampling system, but requires
75 considerable investment in field analytical equipment with typical deployments restricted to
76 arrays of six to twelve sampling points (Harmon et al., 1999). Given that CO₂ fluxes from soils
77 are known to vary spatially, in response to changing soil properties, management, and vegetation
78 (Regina and Alakukku, 2010), and that emissions are also temporally variable, changing
79 diurnally, seasonally and in response to meteorological and disturbance events (Anthony and
80 Silver, 2021), current techniques have serious limitations for quantifying soil biological
81 activity, and new approaches that directly measure microbial decomposition processes in soil are
82 required.

83 To meet the need for *in situ*, highly temporally resolved measurements of microbially driven
84 decomposition our team has developed a low-cost decomposition sensor based on low-cost
85 printed electronics (Atreya et al., 2023). Our previous work has demonstrated that we are able to
86 translate microbial decomposition activity into a change in electrical resistance as a
87 poly(hydroxybutyrate-co-valerate) (PHBV)/carbon composite conductor is degraded (Atreya et
88 al., 2022b). The PHBV biopolymer, which can degrade in both aerobic and anaerobic
89 conditions, is blended with carbon flake to form a printable ink. The ink is screen-printed onto a
90 surface, creating a resistor that is responsive to microbial activity. As microbial activity degrades
91 the polymer, its swelling behavior changes in the presence of soil moisture, driving the carbon
92 particles apart and increasing the resistance over time, with the rate of change in resistance
93 reflecting microbial activity. Thus, the sensors provide a method by which the degradation
94 activity of microbial communities in soil can be more directly measured. Applications of the
95 sensor, thus far, have focused on laboratory evaluations demonstrating proof of concept (Atreya
96 et al., 2023), and a more extensive field application (Whiting et al., submitted). The latter, where

97 44 sensors were deployed for 50 days in a long-term grassland restoration experiment in the UK,
98 demonstrated a positive relationship between sensor response and soil biomass carbon.

99 Here we test the ability of the sensors to track the response of microbial activity to the
100 environmental stress associated with floods and droughts in two contrasting soil and vegetation
101 settings. We then compare and contrast the data from the sensors with traditional methods of
102 assessing microbially mediated activity as a proxy for soil decomposition, including enzymatic
103 activity, soil respiration and soil nutrient concentrations.

104 2 Materials and methods

105 2.1 Experimental Setup

106 Intact cores were collected from two sites near Penrith, north-west England with the same soil
107 type, a sandy loam of the Newport Series (Dystric Arenosol). The first was planted with a
108 monoculture of Winter Wheat (WW) (*Triticum aestivum* L.), (54°45'17"N, 2°47'28"W). The
109 second was a species rich grassland (SRG) (54°43'23"N, 54°43'23"W), which had not been
110 subjected to any chemical inputs in living memory and, given the plant biodiversity, have
111 probably never received fertiliser inputs. The species mix included *Carex flacca*, *Plantago*
112 *lanceolata*, *Lolium perenne*, *Lotus corniculatus* and *Anthoxanthum odoratum*. We collected the
113 cores by inserting sections of pipe into the soil and removing the intact core, to reduce
114 disturbance to the soil. The sections were 15 cm deep with a 10 cm diameter. We collected 18
115 cores from each site on 26th March and a further 18 on 10th April 2024 and placed them in a
116 polytunnel at the Hazelrigg Research Station at Lancaster University (54° 0' 52"N, 2° 46' 40"W).
117 Each pot was assigned a random number, and one of three treatments: drought, flood, or control.
118 The final experimental design was 2 vegetation types x 3 climate treatments x 6 replicates = 36
119 cores. We began the climate treatment on 11th April, and it continued for 32 days, with recovery
120 beginning on the 13th May. For the flood treatment, cores were placed in a tank with rainwater
121 collected from the site, maintained level with the top of the soil throughout the study. For the
122 control, watering with rainwater was administered three times a week, as needed. The drought
123 cores were left to dry down through the treatment phase. When the treatments were alleviated,
124 the flooded cores were allowed to drain, and the drought treatment received one litre of fresh

125 rainwater per pot. For the recovery period, all cores received 500ml twice per week and were
126 allowed to drain freely. Cores were harvested on the 18th June after 36 days of recovery.

127 2.2 Decomposition Sensors

128 Sensors were fabricated through a hybrid printing process comprising a 3D-printed deployment
129 carriage, a conventionally-manufactured printed circuit board (PCB), and stencil-printed ink
130 traces composed of a mixture of Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) and
131 carbon flake. The experimental setup and specific geometries of the sensors deployed are shown
132 in Figure 1. We have described the use of this material as a decomposition sensor in a previous
133 publication (Atreya et al., 2023). Suspended carbon flake makes the ink conductive, and as the
134 PHBV matrix is degraded by soil microbes, the conductivity of the ink changes and can be read
135 as a resistance change by low-cost electronics.

136 The ink was printed directly onto exposed pads on the PCB in a set of three conductive strips,
137 using transfer tape and a razor blade. Each strip was printed in a dogbone geometry with a
138 primary trace width of 1 mm and a length of 25mm. All conductive strips were laid out in
139 parallel, a configuration that controls for stochastic variability or mechanical damage impacting a
140 single trace. Following ink printing, signal conductors were soldered to the PCB before
141 installation in the deployment carriage. The carriage was 3D-printed on a consumer FDM
142 machine (i3MK3, Prusa Research) using a non-dyed PLA filament (Hatchbox). The carriage
143 serves to protect the PCB and ink traces from mechanical damage during installation and
144 provides a potting dam to encapsulate electrical connections. A weatherizing adhesive (FlexSeal)
145 was poured into the potting dam and allowed to cure for at least 48 hours. Between fabrication
146 and deployment, the ink traces were protected using a 3D-printed travel sheath.

147

148

149 Figure 1: Six replicates of six soil type and treatment combinations (left) were instrumented with
 150 decomposition sensors comprising a biodegradable ink printed on a printed circuit board
 151 substrate (center). The sensing surface is assembled within a 3D-printed deployment carriage
 152 which facilitates installation in soil and protects electrical connections with an epoxy dam (right).

153

154 Sensors were deployed in each sample pot using a 3D-printed nylon installation spade in the case
 155 of all treatments except the drought cores. The installation spade creates a pre-formed cavity into
 156 which the sensor is press-fit to encourage good surface contact with the surrounding soil. In the
 157 case of the drought cores, the soil was too dry for this installation method. Instead, soil was
 158 manually excavated to form a cavity large enough for the sensor to be installed, then packed
 159 back down around the sensor. During each sensor's installation, its resistance was monitored
 160 during insertion to ensure that the traces were not mechanically damaged prior to the experiment.

161 Sensor resistances were collected using custom data loggers which use the voltage-divider
 162 principle to calculate the resistances of sensors installed across 6 channels per logger. Resistance
 163 readings were gathered every 30 minutes and logged to an SD card. In this experiment, one
 164 channel from each logger was used to monitor each treatment to avoid any systematic error
 165 introduced by logger electronics and to prevent data loss if a logger were to fail mid-experiment.

166 2.3 Soil Respiration and Covariates

167 Soil moisture and temperature were measured twice per week throughout the treatment and
 168 recovery time using an HH2 Moisture Meter with attached WET-2 sensor (Delta-T Devices,
 169 Cambridge, UK). Soil respiration was measured weekly using an EGM-5 infra-red gas analyser
 170 (IRGA) with attached SRC-2 soil respiration sensor (Hansatech, King's Lynn, UK). We

171 modified the chamber using a piece of pipe 15 cm long to extend the chamber's height and
172 prevent crushing of vegetation. Data were collected in the form of $\text{mg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ hr}^{-1}$.

173 2.4 Plant Analyses

174 Aboveground biomass was collected by cutting all vegetation at the soil surface in each core.
175 The biomass was placed in paper bags and dried at 105 °C for 48 hours before accurately
176 weighing. The root biomass was carefully shaken free of the soil and washed to remove all
177 stones and soil particles. Wheat roots were stored fresh at 5 °C before excision of small cross
178 sections for imaging. The SRG biomass and remaining WW biomass was then dried and
179 weighed as for the aboveground portion.

180 2.5 Soil Analyses

181 The soil was collected and sieved through a 2 mm sieve to remove stones and other debris, then
182 stored at 5 °C until analysis. Gravimetric soil moisture was measured by drying 5g of fresh soil at
183 105 °C for 24 hours and calculating the proportion of water lost. For the microbial biomass
184 carbon and nitrogen, we carried out the chloroform-fumigation method (Brookes et al., 1985).
185 Briefly, 5 g of soil from each core was weighed into a glass vial, and 5 g into a 50 ml Falcon
186 tube. The glass vials were added to a desiccator with a beaker containing 50 ml of chloroform,
187 and a vacuum was applied. The sealed desiccator was left for 24 hours to lyse all microbial cells
188 in the soil samples. At the end of this period, the soil was added to 50 ml Falcon tubes and both
189 fumigated and unfumigated samples were extracted for carbon and nitrogen using 25 ml 0.5 M
190 K_2SO_4 per sample. These were shaken thoroughly on an orbital shaker for 30 minutes at 150
191 rpm. Samples were then filtered through Whatman 42 filter papers and analysed for microbial
192 biomass carbon (MBC) using a Shimadzu TOC analyser (Shimadzu), and for microbial biomass
193 nitrogen using an autoanalyser (AA3, Seal Analytical, UK). The final values were calculated by
194 adjusting for soil moisture, then subtracting the unfumigated from the fumigated portion, and
195 finally adjusting by KEC factor for carbon, and KEN for nitrogen, to account for extraction
196 efficiency (Joergensen, 1996). The dried fraction of soil was ground in a ball mill and analysed
197 for total carbon and nitrogen using an elemental combustion analyser (Elementar Vario EL,
198 Hanau, Germany).

199 Soil extracellular enzymes were assayed using the methods of Jackson et al. (2013) with
200 modifications outlined in Broadbent et al. (2022), which added artificial p-nitrophenyl (pNP)
201 linked substrates to induce a colour reaction through p-nitrophenyl production. The enzymes
202 assayed using this approach were cellobiohydrolase (CBH), β -glucosidase (GLC), N-
203 acetylglucosaminidase (NAG), β -xylosidase (XYL) and acid phosphatase (PHO). CBH and GLC
204 are key enzymes for decomposing cellulose into glucose for microbial uptake. NAG is a step in
205 chitin decomposition, making carbon and nitrogen available for microbes. XYL is part of the
206 decomposition pathway for lignocellulose, and PHO breaks down organic phosphate forms into
207 inorganic forms. We carried out further assays to measure phenol oxidase (POX) and peroxidase
208 (PER), which are instrumental in breaking down complex polyphenols such as lignin and
209 tannins.

210 2.6 Statistical Analysis

211 All data analysis was carried out with R version 4.3.2. To remove spurious readings, a simple
212 filter was applied to remove any resistance readings above 10k Ω prior to any other data
213 processing. To account for differing initial sensor resistances due to the manufacturing process,
214 all sensor signals were normalized: an initial resistance (R_0) was calculated on a per-sensor basis
215 by taking an average of readings within an initial-resistance time window following settling in
216 the soil. A soil settling period began after installation on April 27th at midnight. Next, R_0 was
217 calculated as the sensor-specific resistance between April 28th at midnight and 12 hours later.
218 Each following instantaneous resistance reading was divided by this initial resistance, yielding a
219 normalized resistance (R_{norm}) which we took to be the primary decomposition sensor signal, as
220 we have in previous research (Atreya et al., 2023; Atreya et al., 2022a). Sensor response was
221 characterized by taking sensor slopes for all individual sensors within each treatment window.
222 Sensor slopes are taken to be the linear coefficient of a second-order polynomial model fit to the
223 response of each individual sensor.

224 Most data analysis and visualizations are represented as treatment-specific R_{norm} averages taken
225 at a 24-hour frequency to remove diurnal effects. Sensor standard deviations within each
226 treatment type are shown using error clouds to represent individual sensor variability within each
227 treatment. For all analyses regarding treatment windows, the Treatment Window was taken to be
228 all readings between May 1st and May 13th. A 3-day lag was introduced between physical

229 intervention and the Recovery Window, which was taken to be all readings between May 16th
230 and June 17th.

231 To assess the impact of initial watering treatment on soil samples following a return to control
232 conditions, the soil characteristics at harvest were evaluated using independent t-tests within
233 each combination of soil type and watering treatment.

234 Time series data for soil moisture, temperature, and CO₂ efflux were collected through the course
235 of the experiment (12 sampling dates for VWC and temperature, 6 sampling dates for CO₂
236 efflux). We carried out linear mixed effects models on each of these responses in turn in the *nlme*
237 package in R (Pinheiro et al., 2023; Pinheiro and Bates, 2000) using pot identity as a random
238 factor, and sampling date, soil type and watering treatments as fixed factors with all interactions
239 included. Response data (SMC, temperature and CO₂ efflux) were transformed to meet the
240 assumptions of the model where necessary. These models were not simplified. In the Results
241 section, we represent these measurements in terms of mean value by treatment type, and show
242 the standard deviation error of the readings as error bars.

243 3 Results

244 3.1 Decomposition sensor response to floods and droughts

245 Resistance, as a proxy for microbial activity, showed contrasts according to watering treatments
246 over time (Figure 2a, b and supplementary Figure S1). In the control treatments, where watering
247 was consistent throughout, resistance did not change between the treatment and recovery periods.
248 This was true of both the SRG and WW, although SRG cores became more variable over time
249 (Figure 2c).

250 As expected, sensor decomposition increased sharply with the alleviation of the drought
251 treatment through rewetting in both the SRG and WW cores (Figure 2 a and b) with the rate of
252 increase in normalised resistance significantly higher (Figure 2c) in both treatments.

253 When the flood was removed and the cores allowed to drain, the recovery in the SRG cores was
254 clear as expected, but at a significantly slower rate (Figure 2c) than the recovery from drought
255 (Figures 2 a and b). The flooded WW cores behaved differently. Here the flooding did not slow
256 the rates of decomposition as it had in the SRG cores, with no significant difference found

257 between the treatment and recovery window. In all, apart from the wheat control treatment,
 258 variation between replicates increased after the recovery period started, reaching a maximum
 259 after 30 days.

260

261

262 Figure 2: Over the course of the experiment, sensor responses were characterized in two
 263 decomposition windows: while treatment effects were applied, and during recovery (a).

264 Normalized resistance means are shown across the sensor fleet, where visual examination reveals
 265 dramatic sensor signal changes following the removal of drought and flooding conditions (b).

266 Within the treatment and recovery windows, we examined sensor slope distribution, illustrating
 267 the median with interquartile range (IQR, whiskers represent smallest or largest value within 1.5
 268 x IQR (c), Gives the standard deviation of the sensor readings and where we see a strong
 269 response between treatment and recovery windows for most treatments.

270 3.2 Soil Characteristics

271 Comparing the WW and the SRG soils, pH and activity of the carbon degrading enzymes CBH
 272 and GLC were all significantly higher in the WW Soil, and BGB, soil carbon, total nitrogen and
 273 POX were significantly lower. Few significant effects of the watering treatments were observed
 274 between the measured soil parameters, indicating successful recovery, with the exception of

275 AGB, where in both SRG and WW cores, aboveground biomass was lower in drought cores than
 276 control (Figure 3). Flooding caused a reduction in AGB in WW but not in SRG cores.

277
 278 Figure 3: Laboratory measurements were taken at the end of the experiment to characterize
 279 differences between the two soil types and to examine the recovery of cores which had been
 280 subjected to flood or drought conditions. Box plots represent the median and IQR, whiskers
 281 represent smallest or largest value within 1.5 x IQR. Significance stars reflect comparisons
 282 between the two soil types, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

283 3.3 Environmental parameters

284 Soil volumetric moisture content (Figure 4 a) showed clear differences during the treatment
285 period with the treatments converging during the recovery period. The measured CO₂ flux
286 (Figure 4 c) surprisingly showed no treatment-specific response in the recovery period, with
287 respiration in each of the treatments remaining similar throughout the experiment. No
288 relationship was found between the measured CO₂ flux and the decomposition sensor slope
289 (Supplementary Material Figure S2). No clear signal is visible between Treatment and Control
290 conditions when evaluated purely on CO₂ accumulation slope or integral (Supplementary
291 Material Figure S3). As expected, soil temperatures (Figure 4 b) were on average higher during
292 the drought treatment (average 29.5°C) than during the flooding treatment (average 24.3°C),
293 which follows the expected trend compared to the control treatment (27.3°C on average).
294 Average air temperature captured by the loggers (Figure 4 d) showed a strong diurnal pattern
295 with temperatures reaching a daily mean maximum of 37.3°C and a daily mean minimum of
296 10.7°C.

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300 Figure 4: Environmental parameters were measured throughout the experiment. Air temperature
 301 was collected by on-board sensors in the data loggers, where soil moisture and temperature were
 302 discrete measurements. CO₂ efflux was collected using a collar fitted around each pot. Note that
 303 subplots (a)-(c) include lines only to show trends over time, not to imply continuous
 304 measurements. Error bars are Standard Errors

305

306 4 Discussion

307 By deploying sensors in contrasting soil and vegetation settings which have been exposed to
 308 either a period of drought or waterlogging, we demonstrate in real time how the decomposition
 309 rate changes following the removal of that stress. The data captures nuanced information on
 310 changes in microbial conditions in the soil in a non-destructive manner. Gathering data
 311 destructively at the end of a period of stress and recovery leaves knowledge gaps on the exact
 312 impacts of the stress on microbially-driven activity through the stress. As shown here, a recovery

313 period can obfuscate the overall decomposition rate of soil organic matter by showing apparently
314 similar values in one snapshot of time.

315 Our bespoke soil decomposition sensors were able to respond with a rapid and strong positive
316 shift in resistance, indicating more decomposition of the sensor, following alleviation of
317 environmental stress, with both the SRG and WW treatments showing a similar rate of sensor
318 decomposition throughout the experiment. These responses follow the expected pattern as it is
319 well known that microbial activity sharply increases when osmotic stress is removed (Birch,
320 1958). The main reasons for this are thought to be associated with the release of metabolites due
321 to cell lysis upon rewetting of the soil, which then provide easily decomposable food sources for
322 surviving organisms and the release to protected organic matter (Singh et al., 2023).

323 In the case of flooding, the picture is more complicated. In line with published work, it was
324 expected that flooding would cause significant impacts on soil functioning (Huang et al., 2023;
325 Sánchez-Rodríguez et al., 2019; Tate, 1979). We expected sensor decomposition rates in the
326 flooded cores to be lower than the control, due to anaerobic conditions being established at the
327 sensor, thus slowing or stopping the decomposition activity of aerobic and facultative organisms
328 and that there would steady recovery following the cores being allowed to drain under gravity
329 but that the recovery would be slower than in the droughted treatments. We hypothesize that this
330 due to the slower rate of change in soil moisture following the alleviation of flooding compared
331 to the alleviation of the drought; this is because it takes longer for water to drain from a soil than
332 it takes for a soil to rewet under experimental conditions. This pattern is what we observed in the
333 SRG treatment. In contrast, in the WW the flooding had no negative impact on sensor
334 decomposition rates, in fact decomposition rates were higher throughout the experiment in this
335 treatment combination than in any other treatment including the controls. We hypothesize that
336 this was due to the actively growing wheat plants maintaining an oxygenated rhizosphere which
337 promoted biological activity and thus, sensor decomposition. The oxygenation of the
338 rhizosphere may be due to an adaptation in the wheat plants, perhaps the formation of
339 aerenchyma in response to low oxygen conditions, which has been observed in some wheat
340 varieties (Jin et al., 2025). More work is needed to understand the interactions between the wheat
341 roots, their response to flooding and their interaction with the soil microbial community.

342 The soil analysis we conducted at the end of the experiments was able to show differences
343 between the SRG and the WW cores, but unlike the decomposition sensors they were not able to
344 show differences between the drought, flood and control treatments. The behavior of the soil
345 chemical parameters and enzymes largely conformed to our expectations. The pH was higher in
346 the WW soil as the soil will have been limed to maintain a pH suitable for arable cropping, and
347 within one standard deviation of the mean of 9.94 reported for arable soils in England and Wales
348 (Kirk et al., 2010). The lower pH of 5.5 for the SRG soil is within one standard deviation of the
349 mean of 4.62 for English and Welsh semi-natural grasslands (Kirk et al., 2010). The higher soil
350 carbon and nitrogen contents in the grassland soil are also in line with expectations as the regular
351 disturbance of the arable soil increased aeration and availability of organic carbon for
352 decomposition, and there are lower returns of plant material due to crop harvests. The higher
353 nitrogen content in the grassland soil is perhaps a little surprising, given that the arable soil had
354 regularly received inorganic and organic sources of fertiliser, however offtake by the crop and
355 through leaching is likely to be higher in the arable soil than in the SRG which is essentially a
356 closed system. Activity of hydrolase enzymes (CBH) was higher in WW cores, which is in line
357 with other work that shows hydrolases target the labile C forms prevalent in agricultural soils.
358 Further, activity is lower in soils with a high carbon to nitrogen ratio, as in the SRG soils
359 (Sinsabaugh et al., 2008; Sinsabaugh, 2010). By contrast, oxidases (PER, POX), which were
360 higher in the SRG cores than the WW in our study, target more recalcitrant carbon (Sinsabaugh,
361 2010). SRG contains species which are more conservative in their growth form than arable crops,
362 with slower growth leading to more complex carbon-based structures. Therefore, it is
363 unsurprising that oxidase activity is higher in SRG cores than WW, where crop breeding has
364 served to optimise rapid growth and low investment in roots and long-term structures in favour
365 of high yields of reproductive organs (Poffenbarger et al., 2023). The lack of responses of
366 enzymes or soil nutrients to drought and flooding, while the *in-situ* sensors clearly show strong
367 results, indicates not only recovery of the soil functions, possibly from reassembly of the
368 microbial community, but also the problems inherent in taking all results at harvest.

369 Overall, these data demonstrate the potential benefits of using soil sensors formed from microbe-
370 responsive resistors to continuously monitor and capture dynamic changes in soil decomposition
371 activity. This deployment reinforces the advantages of the material selection and the integrated
372 system design. The composite material used as the microbe responsive material, a blend of the

373 biopolymer poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) and carbon-flake particles,
374 shows a clear, stable response under all the experimental conditions evaluated in this study
375 (control, drought, and flood conditions), and a dynamic change in signal when the experimental
376 conditions are changed. The circuit topology that was used has three of the microbe-responsive
377 resistors (formed from the composite material) stencil-printed directly onto a printed circuit
378 board (PCB), which includes integrated wiring which connects the three resistors in parallel,
379 which shapes the sensor signal to mitigate the impact of spurious resistance changes. Data
380 collected during this experiment demonstrates that this parallelisation approach provides suitable
381 sensitivity and measurement range to capture the differences in microbial activity across the
382 wide range of experimental conditions (particularly moisture levels) that are tested here. Finally,
383 at the system level, the assembly of the sensors into a simple housing and their interrogation
384 using a low-cost electronic system gives a stable and automated response over time, indicating
385 the potential for wide-scale deployability of these devices to capture spatio-temporal variability
386 in soil decomposition activity.

387 Building from this work, there are various potential avenues for future development and
388 understanding of these novel soil sensing devices that are currently being investigated. One
389 interesting line of inquiry is to explore the use of other degradable materials in addition to
390 PHBV, potentially enabling a variety of specific microbial or enzymatic processes to be
391 selectivity monitored. Additionally, carrying out genetic analysis of the microbe-sensitive
392 composite resistor surfaces and surrounding soil to determine the composition of the microbial
393 community responsible for changes in the recorded signal would be beneficial to enhance
394 understanding of the function of the sensors, and to improve the interpretation of the data that
395 they provide. Further long-term field evaluation of the sensors will aid in better understanding
396 the impact of soil management amendments on the sensor signal and the response of the soil
397 microbial community.

398 5 Conclusions

399 We have shown that the sensor response reflects the well-known Birch effect following the
400 alleviation of drought in both a WW and SRG soil and the expected response to flooding in the
401 SRG. The sensors have also produced results which provoke the need for further work in
402 understanding how WW responds to flooding and may alter the rhizosphere environment.

403 This demonstrates that low-cost printable electronic sensors can autonomously track
404 decomposition at high temporal and spatial resolution and offers the potential to explore the
405 dynamics of microbial activity in soils. This has, until now, not been possible without repeated
406 sampling of the target system. Thus, we offer the prospect of a means to study soil microbial
407 community activity fluctuations in situ and without disturbance, beyond inserting the sensor.
408 The low cost and small footprint of the sensors offers the opportunity to deploy multiple sensors
409 across soil types and treatments, allowing us to elucidate the spatial response of decomposition
410 processes to environmental and management changes.

411

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413

414 **Author contributions**

415 JQ led the study and helped to design implement the study with EF. TS and GW built the
416 sensors, TS performed the data analysis. All authors contributed to writing the paper.

417

418 **Data availability**

419 **Data analysis etc. is on the R Markdown site here:** <https://rpubs.com/TaylorSharpe/PolyDecomp>

420

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425

426

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